

Supporting Information for

The dead volume effect in the elastic moduli measurements using the forced-oscillation method

V. Mikhaltsevitch ^{1*}, M. Lebedev¹, R. Chavez², M. Pervukhina³, S. Glubokovskikh¹, and E.A. Vargas Jr.²

¹Department of Exploration Geophysics, Curtin University, Perth, Australia

²Department of Civil Engineering, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

³CSIRO Earth Science and Resource Engineering, Perth, Australia

Contents of this file

Tables S1 to S7

Introduction

This supporting information provides the numerical results of the laboratory experiments conducted on an n-decane saturated limestone sample with varying dead fluid volume. The supporting information includes: (1) the extensional attenuation, Poisson ratio, elastic moduli and strains in the rock measured at 0.1 Hz with the dead volume varying from 2 ml to 260 ml and also with the open fluid line, and (2) the frequency dependences of the attenuation, elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and strains obtained in the frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 120 Hz.

Dead volume, ml	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial Strain x 10 ⁻⁷	Radial Strain x 10 ⁻⁷
2	0.0035	0.266	18.98	13.52	7.50	6.68	1.78
3	0.0033	0.265	18.99	13.48	7.51	6.62	1.75
5	0.0032	0.264	18.97	13.37	7.51	6.67	1.76
6	0.0015	0.259	18.95	13.09	7.53	6.71	1.74
7	0.0027	0.258	18.94	13.06	7.53	6.73	1.74
10	0.0019	0.258	18.92	13.00	7.52	6.74	1.74
15	0.0023	0.258	18.80	12.97	7.47	6.77	1.75
20	0.0011	0.257	18.76	12.85	7.46	6.76	1.74
30	0.0020	0.253	18.56	12.54	7.40	6.78	1.72
50	0.0026	0.251	18.28	12.22	7.31	6.80	1.71
70	0.0037	0.249	18.28	12.15	7.31	6.82	1.70
100	0.0041	0.245	18.22	11.89	7.32	6.84	1.67
125	0.0027	0.245	18.10	11.83	7.27	6.85	1.68
150	0.0024	0.245	18.07	11.81	7.26	6.88	1.68
180	0.0029	0.244	18.11	11.78	7.28	6.83	1.67
190	0.0007	0.242	18.12	11.71	7.29	6.93	1.68
260	0.0007	0.242	18.15	11.71	7.31	6.98	1.69

Table S1. The dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation on dead volume obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnieres limestone at a frequency of 0.1 Hz.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0045	0.242	18.17	11.72	7.32	6.09	1.58
0.2	0.0044	0.239	18.26	11.68	7.37	6.07	1.58
0.4	0.0032	0.245	18.16	11.89	7.29	5.96	1.55
0.6	0.0043	0.239	18.15	11.61	7.32	6.52	1.69
0.8	0.0016	0.243	18.26	11.83	7.35	6.00	1.57
1	0.0030	0.242	18.27	11.80	7.35	5.95	1.55
2	0.0025	0.242	18.41	11.89	7.41	5.97	1.57
4	0.0026	0.242	18.33	11.85	7.38	5.95	1.56
6	0.0079	0.242	18.35	11.86	7.39	6.06	1.59
8	0.0093	0.243	18.31	11.85	7.37	6.05	1.58
10	0.0219	0.244	18.36	11.93	7.38	6.07	1.59
20	0.0744	0.250	18.61	12.42	7.44	6.08	1.62
40	0.1101	0.276	20.06	14.96	7.86	5.83	1.67
60	0.1025	0.278	20.44	15.35	7.99	5.74	1.68
80	0.0679	0.272	20.18	14.73	7.94	5.83	1.68
100	0.0566	0.270	19.82	14.37	7.80	5.84	1.65
120	0.0445	0.271	19.58	14.24	7.70	5.81	1.63

Table S2. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated with the open fluid line.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0031	0.264	19.04	13.45	7.53	6.30	1.66
0.2	0.0024	0.265	19.07	13.50	7.54	6.75	1.79
0.4	0.0022	0.265	19.15	13.60	7.57	6.71	1.78
0.6	0.0018	0.264	19.17	13.56	7.58	6.70	1.77
0.8	0.0025	0.266	19.40	13.81	7.66	6.67	1.77
1	0.0013	0.266	19.28	13.71	7.62	6.62	1.76
2	0.0028	0.265	19.37	13.77	7.65	6.61	1.75
4	0.0011	0.266	19.32	13.76	7.63	6.53	1.74
6	0.0013	0.266	19.22	13.69	7.59	6.62	1.76
8	0.0016	0.266	19.24	13.72	7.60	6.58	1.75
10	0.0019	0.265	19.33	13.72	7.64	6.60	1.75
20	0.0028	0.267	19.53	13.95	7.71	6.61	1.76
40	0.0037	0.268	19.75	14.20	7.79	6.58	1.76
60	0.0029	0.270	19.71	14.29	7.76	6.55	1.77
80	0.0027	0.269	19.66	14.17	7.75	6.56	1.76
100	0.0041	0.270	19.47	14.10	7.67	6.51	1.76
120	0.0038	0.269	19.77	14.26	7.79	6.93	1.86

Table S3. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated at a dead volume of 2 ml.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0017	0.262	19.57	13.71	7.76	6.80	1.78
0.2	0.0029	0.260	19.52	13.58	7.74	6.76	1.76
0.4	0.0011	0.262	19.29	13.53	7.64	6.75	1.77
0.6	0.0033	0.264	19.30	13.64	7.63	6.75	1.78
0.8	0.0022	0.263	19.54	13.74	7.74	6.70	1.76
1	0.0011	0.262	19.53	13.67	7.74	6.64	1.74
2	0.0016	0.262	19.41	13.62	7.69	6.61	1.74
4	0.0028	0.263	19.48	13.69	7.71	6.53	1.72
6	0.0012	0.267	19.60	14.02	7.73	6.63	1.77
8	0.0017	0.264	19.67	13.87	7.78	6.60	1.74
10	0.0018	0.266	19.84	14.16	7.83	6.59	1.76
20	0.0030	0.266	19.81	14.11	7.82	6.64	1.77
40	0.0035	0.265	19.89	14.08	7.86	6.61	1.75
60	0.0036	0.266	19.79	14.07	7.82	6.59	1.75
80	0.0031	0.264	19.52	13.77	7.72	6.62	1.75
100	0.0027	0.263	19.40	13.65	7.68	6.59	1.73
120	0.0025	0.263	19.63	13.79	7.77	6.48	1.70

Table S4. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated at a dead volume of 5 ml.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0042	0.251	18.35	12.28	7.33	6.99	1.75
0.2	0.0023	0.251	18.47	12.36	7.38	6.93	1.74
0.4	-0.0001	0.251	18.44	12.33	7.37	6.91	1.73
0.6	0.0031	0.251	18.47	12.34	7.38	6.89	1.73
0.8	0.0012	0.252	18.48	12.41	7.38	6.87	1.73
1	0.0016	0.252	18.47	12.41	7.38	6.81	1.71
2	0.0028	0.252	18.46	12.40	7.37	6.79	1.71
4	0.0004	0.252	18.51	12.44	7.39	6.71	1.69
6	0.0014	0.251	18.45	12.37	7.37	6.79	1.71
8	0.0049	0.252	18.45	12.37	7.37	6.73	1.69
10	0.0059	0.250	18.46	12.30	7.39	6.75	1.69
20	0.0145	0.248	18.24	12.05	7.31	6.82	1.69
40	0.0660	0.258	18.45	12.73	7.33	6.73	1.74
60	0.0358	0.275	19.57	14.49	7.67	6.56	1.80
80	0.0217	0.272	19.56	14.27	7.69	6.52	1.77
100	0.0096	0.273	19.18	14.06	7.54	6.44	1.76
120	0.0043	0.264	19.03	13.46	7.53	5.01	1.32

Table S5. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated at a dead volume of 30 ml.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0047	0.245	17.97	11.72	7.22	6.99	1.71
0.2	0.0009	0.245	17.87	11.67	7.18	6.99	1.71
0.4	0.0000	0.246	18.13	11.88	7.28	6.95	1.71
0.6	0.0001	0.245	18.15	11.86	7.29	6.93	1.70
0.8	-0.0010	0.245	18.10	11.81	7.27	6.92	1.69
1	0.0028	0.245	18.15	11.84	7.29	6.86	1.68
2	0.0035	0.245	18.16	11.85	7.30	6.84	1.67
4	0.0002	0.244	18.19	11.86	7.31	6.75	1.65
6	0.0060	0.244	18.11	11.81	7.28	6.84	1.67
8	0.0066	0.244	18.12	11.78	7.28	6.81	1.66
10	0.0125	0.242	18.11	11.70	7.29	6.84	1.65
20	0.0371	0.241	17.75	11.43	7.15	6.93	1.67
40	0.0780	0.270	19.09	13.84	7.52	6.64	1.79
60	0.0545	0.277	19.53	14.59	7.65	6.51	1.80
80	0.0421	0.273	19.42	14.28	7.63	6.51	1.78
100	0.0327	0.274	18.99	14.03	7.45	6.45	1.77
120	0.0229	0.276	19.01	14.15	7.45	5.52	1.52

Table S6. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated at a dead volume of 100 ml.

Frequency, Hz	Extensional attenuation	Poisson ratio	Young's modulus, GPa	Bulk modulus, GPa	Shear modulus, GPa	Axial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$	Radial strain, $\times 10^{-7}$
0.1	0.0016	0.242	18.15	11.71	7.31	6.98	1.69
0.2	0.0021	0.243	18.36	11.90	7.39	6.94	1.69
0.4	0.0048	0.245	18.23	11.91	7.32	6.96	1.71
0.6	0.0028	0.244	18.47	12.01	7.43	6.94	1.69
0.8	0.0025	0.242	18.42	11.91	7.41	6.91	1.67
1	0.0052	0.241	18.48	11.89	7.45	6.85	1.65
2	0.0023	0.241	18.66	12.01	7.52	6.83	1.65
4	0.0060	0.241	18.70	12.04	7.53	6.77	1.63
6	0.0118	0.241	18.64	12.01	7.51	6.87	1.66
8	0.0158	0.241	18.62	11.97	7.50	6.84	1.65
10	0.0202	0.240	18.58	11.91	7.49	6.87	1.65
20	0.0696	0.244	18.35	11.95	7.38	6.91	1.69
40	0.0994	0.274	20.00	14.72	7.85	6.59	1.80
60	0.0863	0.277	20.24	15.10	7.93	6.49	1.80
80	0.0664	0.273	20.16	14.78	7.92	6.51	1.78
100	0.0548	0.273	20.06	14.74	7.88	6.46	1.76
120	0.0483	0.271	19.94	14.52	7.84	6.78	1.84

Table S7. The frequency dependences of the elastic moduli, Poisson ratio and extensional attenuation obtained for n-decane saturated Savonnières limestone saturated at a dead volume of 260 ml.